

Synthesis of Some Furan-2-aldoxime Complexes of Copper(II) Derived from Various Tetrathiocyanato-disubstituted Chromate(III) Ions

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A series of the complexes of type $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L})_2]_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L}')_2]_2$, where FDH = furan-2-aldoxime, L = ammonia, aniline, *p*-toluidine, β - or γ -picoline, urea, thiourea, and L' = ethylenediamine, propylenediamine, *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl, have been prepared. The molar conductances of complexes in water ($250 \Omega^{-1}$) indicate three ions. The sites of the coordination of various ligands to metal ions were decided with the help of spectral data ($4000\text{-}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

THE study of such complexes, in which both cation and anion are complex ions, is interesting as it provides an opportunity to study various configurations forced together in one complex moiety. During the course of such a study some complexes of metal(II) nitroprussides and ferrocyanides were prepared and reported¹⁻³. In the present paper we report the preparations and spectral data of a series of complexes of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L})_2]_2$ or $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L}')_2]_2$ where L = ammonia, aniline, *p*-toluidine, β - and γ -picoline, urea or thiourea, and L' = ethylenediamine (en), propylenediamine (pn), *o*-phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy). Conclusive evidence for the coordination of oxime to copper(II), and thiocyanate or other ligands to chromium(III) has been obtained from infrared spectral studies while the geometries of the complexes have been inferred by magnetic and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

The preparation of complexes involves four steps.

(i) *Furan-2-carbaldoxime*: The oxime was prepared by standard method using furan-2-carbaldehyde and hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁴.

(ii) *Bisfuran-2-carbaldoxime copper(II) chloride*, $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$: Copper(II) chloride (13.35 g, 1 mol) suspended in methanol (100 ml) was treated with the oxime (22.2 g, 2 mol). The solution was refluxed for 6 h and the complex obtained was crystallised out by the repeated treatments with petroleum ether (b.p. $60\text{-}80^\circ$).

(iii) *Tetrathiocyanato-disubstituted chromate(III) salts*:

(a) *Compounds of type $\text{H}^+[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L})_2]$* : Anhydrous $\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_6]$ (5.21 g, 1 mol) was treated with either ammonia (0.321 g), aniline (1.85 g), *p*-toluidine (2.14 g) or picoline (1.86 g, 2 mol). Reactants were heated on a water bath for 3 h⁵. The compounds were precipitated out from the red coloured mass by adding acetic acid solution (20%), and crystallised with ethanol.

(b) *Compounds of type $\text{K}[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L}) \text{ or } (\text{L}')]$* : Chrome alum (6.84 g), potassium thiocyanate (3.88 g) and either urea (1.20 g) or thiourea (1.52 g) in 1 : 4 : 2 molar ratio were dissolved in hot water. The mixture was evaporated slowly and the dried mass was extracted with ethanol⁶. The solution was concentrated when red-violet crystals were formed and recrystallised with ethanol. The same method was employed for ethylene or propylene diamine complex using 0.60 or 0.74 mol of the amine in accordance with 1 : 4 : 1 ratio.

(c) *Complexes of type $\text{K}[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L}')]$* : Anhydrous $\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_6]$ (5.21 g, 1 mol) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (20 ml), and *o*-phenanthroline (1.52 g) or 1.34 g of 2,2'-dipyridyl (1.34 g, 1 mol) was added to the suspension, and the mixture was digested on a water bath for 2 h⁷. The solution was filtered out, concentrated and left overnight. Needle shaped pink crystals obtained were filtered and recrystallised with ethanol.

(iv) *Preparation of bisfuran-2-carbaldoxime copper(II)tetrathiocyanato-disubstituted chromate(III)*, $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L})_2 \text{ or } (\text{L}')_2]$: The complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$ (3.55 g, 1 mol) was treated with any

uni-negative tetrathiocyanato-disubstituted chromate (III) salt (2 mol). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The crystals of the new complex so obtained were filtered, washed, dried and analysed.

Copper and chromium were estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate and barium chromate, respectively and thiocyanate was estimated volumetrically using standard silver nitrate solu-

tion⁸. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated microanalytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The molar conductances were measured in water on Toshniwal CLOIO2A instrument. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibilities and electronic spectra were recorded at the Guru Nanak Dev University. The data are given in Table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF VARIOUS TETRATHIOCYANATO-DISUBSTITUTED CHROMATE(III) SALTS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					λ (in water) Ω^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Cr	NCS	C	H	N		
1.	$[C_6H_5NH_2][Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_5NH_2)_2]$	Pink red	8.82 (9.22)	40.85 (41.13)	43.82 (46.80)	4.51 (3.90)	7.26 (7.44)	110	3.89
2.	$[p-CH_3C_6H_4NH_2][Cr(NCS)_4(p-CH_3C_6H_4NH_2)_2]$	Pink red	8.37 (8.28)	38.23 (38.28)	48.85 (49.50)	4.86 (4.62)	6.12 (6.93)	Insoluble	3.92
3.	$[\beta-CH_3C_6H_4NH_2][Cr(NCS)_4(\beta-pic)_2]$	Pink	9.12 (9.22)	40.86 (41.13)	45.75 (46.80)	4.42 (3.90)	7.23 (7.44)	Insoluble	3.80
4.	$[\gamma-CH_3-C_6H_4NH_2][Cr(NCS)_4(\gamma-pic)_2]$	Pink	8.93 (9.22)	40.70 (41.13)	46.15 (46.80)	4.36 (3.90)	7.26 (7.44)	Insoluble	4.02
5.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(urea)_2]$	Red	11.67 (11.73)	51.03 (52.37)	15.93 (16.25)	2.83 (1.80)	12.56 (12.64)	128	3.92
6.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(tu)_2]^*$	Red	10.35 (10.99)	48.21 (48.84)	14.12 (15.15)	2.36 (1.68)	11.39 (11.78)	130	3.79
7.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(en)]$	Red	13.17 (13.57)	60.26 (60.57)	18.15 (18.79)	2.86 (2.08)	6.93 (7.31)	126	4.21
8.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(pn)]$	Red	11.12 (11.29)	49.20 (50.38)	22.88 (23.45)	2.83 (2.38)	20.98 (21.28)	120	4.08
9.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(ophen)]$	Pink	9.63 (10.33)	45.70 (46.12)	37.44 (38.17)	2.51 (1.59)	5.34 (5.56)	Insoluble	4.10
10.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(dipy)]$	Pink	10.22 (10.85)	47.93 (48.43)	52.83 (53.07)	2.37 (1.67)	5.12 (5.84)	Insoluble	3.82
11.	$NH_4[Cr(NCS)_4(NH_2)_2]$	Red	15.47 (14.93)	67.31 (68.52)	14.20 (14.28)	2.97 (3.78)	12.33 (12.50)	141	3.80

* tu = Thiourea.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF NEW OXIME COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					λ (in water) Ω^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Cr	NCS	C	H	N		
1.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_5NH_2)_2]$	Brown	8.06 (8.49)	37.18 (37.87)	40.82 (41.14)	3.31 (3.10)	15.76 (16.00)	235	5.80
2.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(p-CH_3C_6H_4NH_2)_2]$	Brown	7.78 (8.12)	36.08 (36.22)	42.83 (43.09)	3.72 (3.59)	15.13 (15.30)	260	6.02
3.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(\beta-C_6H_7M)_2]$	Yellow	8.12 (8.49)	37.12 (37.87)	40.89 (41.14)	3.34 (3.10)	15.83 (16.00)	Insoluble	5.68
4.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(\gamma-C_6H_7N)_2]$	Yellow	8.08 (8.49)	37.20 (37.87)	40.72 (41.14)	3.36 (3.10)	15.78 (16.00)	Insoluble	5.95
5.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(urea)_2]$	Yellow	9.13 (9.51)	41.81 (42.45)	24.05 (24.12)	2.71 (2.37)	22.56 (23.05)	Insoluble	5.90
6.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(thiourea)_2]$	Yellow	8.29 (8.98)	40.00 (40.10)	22.26 (22.81)	2.64 (2.24)	21.23 (21.78)	260	5.82
7.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(en)]_2$	Yellow	9.81 (10.68)	47.30 (47.68)	27.10 (27.13)	3.10 (2.67)	19.04 (20.14)	255	6.31
8.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(pn)]_2$	Yellow	9.86 (10.38)	46.15 (46.35)	28.12 (28.77)	3.72 (2.99)	19.15 (19.58)	Insoluble	6.25
9.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(phen)]_2$	Yellow	8.13 (8.57)	37.82 (38.25)	40.48 (41.55)	2.75 (2.14)	15.78 (16.15)	225	6.08
10.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(dipy)]_2$	Yellow	8.26 (8.92)	38.92 (39.82)	38.83 (39.14)	2.80 (2.23)	15.85 (16.82)	Insoluble	5.92
11.	$[Cu(FDH)_2][Cr(NCS)_4(NH_2)_2]$	Yellow	11.12 (10.29)	49.20 (50.38)	22.88 (23.45)	2.83 (2.38)	20.98 (21.28)	247	5.88

Results and Discussion

The analytical and molar conductance data suggest the molecular formulae of the complexes to be $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})_2][\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{L})_2 \text{ or } (\text{L}')_2]$. The evidence for the coordination of ligands as FDH to copper(II) and thiocyanate, L or L' to chromium(III) is obtained from the infrared data.

Ir spectra of β -furan-2-carbaldoxime: The ligand, furan-2-oxime can exist in two geometrical forms as shown below.

Sym or α -oxime

Anti or β -oxime

In the ir spectrum of free antioxime, two bands are observed at 3160 and 3040 cm^{-1} assigned to the intramolecularly bonded OH group, which are observed in complexes at 3360 cm^{-1} . The C=N stretching frequency in free oxime is observed at 1640 cm^{-1} which is shifted to $1660 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes, due to the increase in its bond order on coordination^{9,10}. In free ligand, no band is observed below 700 cm^{-1} , while in complexes two distinct bands are seen at 670 and 510 cm^{-1} assigned to Cu-O (oxime) and Cu-O (furan ring) stretches¹¹⁻¹³. These observations establish the coordination of oxime through oxime and furan ring oxygen atoms.

Ir spectra of other ligands: The coordination of thiocyanate ion through nitrogen and thiourea through sulfur is indicated by the presence of ν_{CN} at 2080 or 1500 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ at 748 or 750 cm^{-1} , respectively in the complexes¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

In case of aniline, *p*-toluidine, ethylene or propylene diamine complexes coordination of amine is inferred by the lowering of the ν_{NH} stretch which occurs at 3200 cm^{-1} in complexes¹⁸⁻²⁰. The evidence for the coordination of *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl is obtained from the positive shifts in the position of C=C, C=N, ring stretchings; C-H in plane deformation and ring breathing vibrations, which in free ligands occur at 1610, 1500, 1470 cm^{-1} and 1370, 1250, 1220 cm^{-1} , respectively²¹⁻²³.

All the complexes are highly paramagnetic in nature due to their spin-free configurations. The

magnetic moments for various tetrathiocyanato-disubstituted chromium(III) salts (Table 1) around 3.89 B.M., correspond to the usual three unpaired electron value for chromium(III) ion, while the value for the copper complexes are very high (5.80 B.M.) due the four unpaired electrons of the two metal ions. Subtracting the μ_{eff} value of the individual chromium(III) complex, gives resultant value around 1.90 B.M. for the complexes which is the normal magnetic moment value for planar copper(II) complex ion. The characteristic d-d band of copper(II) (Cr^{III} bands being at 25.00, 19.00 and 13.50 kK) is observed at 15.40 kK, in the form of a broad band. The D_a values around 1540 cm^{-1} indicate that the oxime is a sufficiently strong ligand.

References

- G. NARAIN, T. M. AGNIHOTRI and P. R. SHUKLA, in the press.
- G. NARAIN, A. M. SHAKYA and P. R. SHUKLA, in the press.
- G. NARAIN, T. M. AGNIHOTRI and P. R. SHUKLA, in the press.
- O. L. BRADY and R. F. GOLDSTEIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1954.
- M. A. BENNETT, R. J. H. CLARK and A. D. J. GOODWIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 1625.
- G. COUTREAS and R. SCHIMIDT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 127.
- P. PFEIFFER and B. WERDELMANN, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1965, 235, 263.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", E.L.B.S., London, 1978, pp. 510, 453, 339.
- K. BURGER, "Coordination Chemistry Experimental Methods", Butterworth, London, 1973, p. 67.
- K. BURGER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 27, 2361.
- R. A. KRAUSE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 2216.
- G. LEES, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1971, 337.
- K. BURGER, R. RUFF and J. RUFF, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1960, 40.
- S. GURU, B. K. MOHAPATRA and B. PAUL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 337.
- I. NAKAGAWA and S. MIZUSHIMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1955, 28, 589.
- A. YAMAGUCHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 527.
- N. R. KUNCHUR and M. R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3478.
- M. A. J. JUNG BAUR and C. CURRAN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 141.
- C. N. R. RAO and R. VENKATRAGHVAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, 39, 1757.
- M. P. COAKLAY, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 1984.
- F. A. COTTON, D. D. FANT, D. M. L. GOODGAME and R. H. HOLM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1780.
- N. N. GREENWOOD and K. WADE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1130.
- N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTHALL, D. E. SCAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 18, 79.